

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE PERFORMANCE OF FOUR TEST CLONES OF TEA

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Abstract

The present experiment was carried out to study the performances of four vegetatively propagated test clones of tea namely Ph/9/68A, Sh/D/11/18, A/8/61 and SC/12/28 with very popular clone named BT2 as control. Morphologically test clone Sh/D/11/18 is the light-leaved Assam agrotype which is key indicator for better quality while test clone SC/12/28 is China Monipuri Hybrid agrotype is for more drought tolerance. It was also found that, Sh/D/11/18 and SC/12/28 both test clones possess excellent (90-95%) rooting ability. In case of yield performance at mature stage, test clone SC/12/28 appeared superior (3341.75 kg ha⁻¹) to other test clones which was followed by A/8/61 (3320.37 kg ha⁻¹) and Sh/D/11/18 (3304.15 kg ha⁻¹), production of both A/8/61 and Sh/D/11/18 test clones were statistically similar. However, in quality parameters, Sh/D/11/18 test clone has been found to be 'Excellent' cup quality. On the other hand, SC/12/28 has been observed to be highly tolerant to drought while Sh/D/11/18 was found to be drought hardy than other test clones. Considering the morphological, yield, quality and drought parameters, test clone Sh/D/11/18 were released as 'Improved Quality Clone' as 'BT22' while SC/12/28 were released as 'Drought Tolerant Standard Clone' as 'BT23' in the BT-series to the industry in 2021.

Keywords: Tea, Yield performance, Cup quality, Test clones

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Introduction

The tea plant, *Camellia sinensis* (L.) O. Kuntze, is a woody plant that is indigenous to China and belongs to the genus *Camellia* of the family Theaceae (Chang & Bartholomew, 1984; Taniguchi et al., 2012). Due to its therapeutic benefits, tea has become one of the most popular non-alcoholic beverages in the world. Its appeal as a "health drink" has increased significantly day-by-day. The tea sector in Bangladesh contributes 1% of the country's GDP, making it one of the main sources of revenue for the national treasury (Raza, 2019).

With a grant area of 285139.39 acres and a tea area of 152256.61 acres, there are currently 166 tea estates in Bangladesh (PDU, 2020). In 1947, there were 28,734 ha of tea cultivation, producing 18.36 million kg, with a yield of 656 kg per hectare. By 2020, however, there were 62,168.46 ha of tea cultivation, producing 86.39 million kg, with a yield of 1561 kg per hectare (BTB, 2021). In contrast to the global situation, tea exports and production in Bangladesh is negatively correlated. About 30.98 million kg of tea were exported in 1980; by 2020, that number had dropped to approximately 2.17 million kg, a 92.99% decline. This point of view implies the need to increase production with improved export-quality liquor and to investigate alternate strategies for boosting tea export and cultivation profits. Our tea industry also facing problem of low production due to prolonged drought period during last couple of years. In order to address consumer demand and maximize tea growers' profit margins, it is urgently necessary to concentrate on varietal development in Bangladesh that combines high production, better quality and severe drought tolerance.

Since the beginnings of BTRI, it has put emphasis on clonal selection and hybridization programs with the goal of developing planting materials that have the potential to be high-yielding, high-quality and drought resistant. The program for clonal selection has begun in 1959 while hybridization in 1965 (Rashid & Alam, 1990). As a result of these efforts, the institution has so far provided the industry with twenty-three vegetative clones of BT-series. In the current investigation, four vegetatively propagated test clones of tea were compared to a control BT2 to examine the long-term yield, quality and drought performances.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out with four test clones of tea in the experimental field of BTRI, during the period from 2007 to 2020. During rooting trial, rooting ability of particular each test clones were calculated by the equation; rooting ability = (Cuttings survived)/ (Total cutting planted) X 100. After rooting trial in the nursery, the selected test clones, namely Ph/9/68A, Sh/D/11/18, A/8/61 and SC/12/28 were put to long term yield and quality trial during 2007 at BTRI Farm. The experiment was laid out in a 5 m x 5 m Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 105 cm x 60 cm spacing of plot size and each plot had a total of 25 plants. For the purpose of comparing yield, quality and other parameters, BTRI released standard variety BT2 has been used as control. In a rain-fed environment, the experiment was carried out. Application of the fertilizer mixture was followed as BTRI instructions (BTRI, 1994; BTRI, 1998). As per BTRI guidelines, young and mature tea pruning was practiced for young tea: Decentre-Prune-Skiff-Prune-Skiff (BTRI, 1986) and for mature tea: Light prune-Deep skiff-Medium skiff-Light skiff (BTRI, 2002). Throughout the experimental period, the green leaves of per plot was plucked at weekly intervals from mid-March to mid-December. The amount of made tea produced (kg ha⁻¹) was estimated using a 23% recovery rate from green leaves. The clonal category (yield or standard or quality clone) of a particular tea clone was done on the basis of 'yield' and 'cup quality' as follow:

Table 1. The categories of tea clones as yield, standard and quality clones.

Category of clones	Yield clone	Standard clone	Quality clone
Yield (made tea kg ha ⁻¹)	>4000 kg ha ⁻¹	3000-4000 kg ha ⁻¹	2500-3000 kg ha ⁻¹
Cup Quality	AA* or A*	AA*	E*
Category of clones	Yield clone	Standard clone	Quality clone

* Quality score: E = Excellent (>34 out of 50)

AA = above average (32 to <34 out of 50)

A = average (30 to < out of 50)

BA = Below Average (<30 out of 50).

The traditional organoleptic tasting procedure was used to evaluate the organoleptic quality of manufactured teas of each test clones and scoring was done on the basis of liquor characteristics (BTRI, 2009; BTRI, 2021). In order to make the liquor, boiling water was poured into a mug with a 142 ml (0.25 pint) capacity which contained 2.5 g of tea. The liquor was then poured into a bowl after 5 minutes of brewing as well as the infused leaf had to be taken from the mug into the inverted lid, which was then placed on top of the mug. Both the infused leaf and the liquor were then tasted by taster panel. Infused leaf appearance and liquor characteristics were assessed by scoring numerically out of 50 points as below:

- Infusion (10)
- Liquor characteristics (40 points): Liquor colour (10 points), Briskness (10 points), Strength (10 points), Creaming down (10 points)

Five plant samples from each test clone with each replication were taken during the third year of the experiment to measure the average depth of root and root shoot ratio in order to evaluate the drought performance. Lychor was used to measure leaf water potential, rate of photosynthesis, transpiration loss and water usage efficiency. Leaf samples were extracted using 3% aqueous sulfosalicylic acid to determine their proline concentration. Two milliliters of the filtered solution were pipetted into the test tube, along with two milliliters of acid ninhydrin and glacial acetic acid. A UV spectrophotometer was used to quantify the separated toluene at 520 nm in comparison to a reagent blank after being incubated at hot bathing and ice bathing. By using a leaf and diluted methanolic extract, total chlorophyll (sum of chlorophyll a & chlorophyll b) was computed and measured at 470, 653 and 666 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer with methanol used as a blank. The relative leaf water content was determined using the Barr & Weatherley (1962), and the Chlorophyll stability index was computed using the following equation generated by Kaloyereas (1958). Chlorophyll Stability Index (%) = (Optical density value of heated sample / Optical density value of unheated sample) X 100. All data were compiled and analyzed statistically in MSTAT program in a microcomputer. The Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to compare means after the analysis of variance was calculated.

Results and Discussion

General and morphological characteristics

General characteristics of four test clones (Ph/9/68A, Sh/D/11/18, A/8/61 and SC/12/28) and control BT2 is given in Table 02. From Table 02, it was observed that, test clone Sh/D/11/18 is the light-leaved Assam agrotype while test clone SC/12/28 is China Monipuri Hybrid agrotype. Wellensiek (1947) observed that a better tea quality was found in light green leaves of Assam agrotypes while Manipuri types was for drought tolerance (Greenway, 1945). Pruning recovery of all the test clones were high. It was also found that Sh/D/11/18 and SC/12/28 both test clones possess excellent rooting ability (Figure 1 of Appendix I).

Table 2. General characteristics of four test clones and BT2 as control.

Test clones	Bush characters	Leaf type	Pruning recovery	Nursery rooting (%)
Ph/9/68A	Plago-orthotropic, compact bush, densely branched with heavy girth and quite satisfactory spread.	Prominent long apex, uniformly serrated, leaf blade is quite embossed and slightly wavy.	High	80-85%
Sh/D/11/18	The plant falls under light-leaved Assam agrotype, semi-orthotropic, plucking shoots are soft, medium sized, dense and evenly distributed on the plucking table.	Leaves are light green, broad in size, glossy and smooth with semi-erect leaf pose. Leaf apex is prominent with uniformly serrated margin.	High	90-95%
A/8/61	Ortho-plagiotropic, compact plucking table, fairly dense plucking points, heavy girth with good branching behaviour	Leaves are light green, broad in size, texture is thick, soft and leathery, and apex is less prominent, leaf pose semi horizontal.	High	80-85%
SC/12/28	China Monipuri Hybrid agrotype with heavy girth and quite satisfactory spread and profuse branching. The plant has medium bush with orthotropic growth habit.	Leaves are dark green, medium to broad in size, glossy and smooth with semi-erect leaf pose. Leaf apex is prominent with uniformly serrated margin.	High	90-95%
BT2	Orthotropic, densely branched, comparatively loose frame, but effective branches, very well and uniform flushing behaviour, moderately floriferous.	Leaf texture fairly thick and soft, semi-dark green. Apex less pointed, lamina considerably equal width in mid region, serration uniform and semi-erect.	High	85-90%

Note: Rooting ability: Excellent = >90%, Good= >80% - <90%, Medium= <70% - 80%

Pruning recovery: High, very good, good, fair/moderate

Some morphological characteristics are provided in Table 3. It was observed that 100 fresh shoot weight, shoot length, leaf area, lamina length, serration/leaf, pruning sticks/bush at FFP-2 and plucking point /bush/year were significantly differs within the test clones. Test clone Sh/D/11/18, A/8/61 and SC/12/28 gave higher results in most cases than the control BT2.

Table 3. Morphological characteristics of four test clones and BT2 as control.

Characteristics	Ph/9/68A	Sh/D/11/18	A/8/61	SC/12/28	BT2	LSD at 5% level of significance
100 fresh shoot weight (g) (2L+B)	83.45b	91.35a	91.34a	91.75a	87.55ab	3.56
Shoot dry matter (%)	21.32	22.41	22.11	22.63	22.25	NS
Shoot length (cm)- (2L+B)	7.11b	7.98a	7.15b	7.85ab	7.13b	0.43
Mature leaf area (cm ²)	41.43b	45.39a	42.34ab	42.14ab	35.25c	2.11
Leaf lamina length (cm)	11.34c	14.75a	11.33c	13.62b	12.15ab	1.21
Leaf lamina breadth (cm)	6.31	6.28	6.38	6.45	5.39	NS
No. of bullation/leaf	12.33	12.36	11.37	12.41	11.43	NS
No. of serration/leaf	67.53c	75.47b	69.65bc	79.65a	78.22ab	2.31
No. of pruning sticks/bush at FFP-2	15.69bc	17.26ab	17.31ab	18.31a	16.35b	1.02
Wt (kg) of pruning litter/bush at FFP-2	1.17	1.43	1.13	1.28	1.21	NS
Number of plucking point /bush/year	461b	487ab	489ab	512a	494ab	5.85

Within row values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

NS= Not Significant

Yield performance

The made tea production (kg ha⁻¹) are presented in Table 4 for immature stage. From Table 4 it reveals that at initial stage of growth, control BT2 (1544.75 kg ha⁻¹) showed significant higher average yield trend than rest of the test clones. Made tea production of test clone SC/12/28 (1259.89 kg ha⁻¹) and A/8/61 (1259.89 kg ha⁻¹) were statistically similar and followed by Sh/D/11/18 (1172.66 kg ha⁻¹). Lowest production was observed by test clone Ph/9/68A (989.43 kg ha⁻¹).

Table 4. Made tea production (kg ha⁻¹) of four test clone and their control at immature stage.

Test Clones	3 rd Year	4 th Year	5 th Year	Average
	UP (2008)	Pruned (2009)	Skiff (2010)	
Ph/9/68A	1044.27c	604c	1321ab	989.43c
Sh/D/11/18	1251.98bc	892b	2225c	1172.66bc
A/8/61	1210.26bc	573c	1996a	1259.89b
SC/12/28	1476.68b	619c	1618b	1274.12b
BT2	1740.15a	1072a	1693b	1544.75a
LSD at 0.05 level of significance	146.86	158.22	186.34	91.46

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

Year wise made tea production (kg ha⁻¹) are presented in Table 5 for mature stage. Highest average made tea was obtained from test clone SC/12/28 (3341.75 kg ha⁻¹) which is followed by A/8/61 (3320.37 kg ha⁻¹) and Sh/D/11/18 (3304.15 kg ha⁻¹); production of both test clones A/8/61 and Sh/D/11/18 (Figure 2 of Appendix I) were statistically similar and higher than control BT2 (3051.25 kg ha⁻¹). Lowest average production was found in test clone Ph/9/68A (2764.35 kg ha⁻¹).

Table 5. Made tea production (kg ha⁻¹) of four test clone and their control at mature stage.

Test Clones	2016	2017	2018	2019	Average
	DSK	MSK	LSK	LP	
Ph/9/68A	2633.0a	2310.4e	3480.32bc	2633.7b	2764.35c
Sh/D/11/18	2598.3b	3509.1b	3879.41ab	3229.8a	3304.15ab
A/8/61	3336.3ab	3226.1c	3572.80b	3146.3ab	3320.37ab
SC/12/28	3275.5ab	3007.9d	3955.40a	3128.2ab	3341.75a
BT2	3112.5c	3612.0a	3314.10c	2166.4c	3051.25b
LSD at 0.05 level of significance	156.34	178.95	207.43	145.64	108.57

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

Quality performance

As determined by traditional organoleptic test, Table 6 illustrates the overall quality of test clones in comparison to the BT2 as control. All the test clones and the control were found to be of "Above average" cup quality except Sh/D/11/18. Test clone Sh/D/11/18 possess bright infusion with very useful strength and briskness. It has excellent creaming down quality (Figure 3 of Appendix I). From the quality category of Table 01 and the total scoring of Sh/D/11/18 from Table 6, it can be categorized as 'excellent quality' (having 34 or more than 34 quality score out of 50 is considered as excellent quality).

Table 6. Cup quality of different test clones and their control.

Test Clones	Infusion (10)	Liquor Colour (10)	Briskness (10)	Strength (10)	Creaming down (10)	Total (50)	Remarks
Ph/9/68A	7.48 ab	7.38 bc	7.64 b	7.28 d	2.61 d	32.39 bc	AA
Sh/D/11/18	7.49 a	7.41 ab	7.55 c	7.52 b	4.51 a	34.48 a	E
A/8/61	7.44 b	7.32 c	7.42 d	7.39 c	2.84 b	32.41 bc	AA
SC/12/28	7.22 c	7.41 ab	7.66 ab	7.27 d	2.82 b	32.38 c	AA
BT2	7.28 bc	7.46 a	7.68 a	7.72 a	2.71 c	32.85 b	AA
LSD at 5% level of significance	0.003	0.06	0.005	0.06	0.008	0.11	

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

A: Average, AA: Above Average, E: Excellent cup quality

There are many factors affecting liquor quality of a particular test clone. Number of pubescence and length of a single unopen bud are most fundamental criteria for liquor quality. Variety with numerous pubescence provide better 'cup quality' liquor (Wilson & Clifford, 1992) while variety with larger leaf bud has special interest for white tea and orthodox tea manufacturing. Number of pubescence and length of a single unopen bud of this experiment are given in Table 7. It was observed that, highest pubescence number was found Sh/D/11/18 test clone (1725) which is followed by SC/12/28 (1631). Higher number of pubescence of the test clone Sh/D/11/18 is the main reason for being 'excellent quality'. On the other hand, test clone SC/12/28 could have special interest of the tea planters for white tea and orthodox tea manufacturing for having longest leaf bud (4.31 cm) amongst the test clones (Figure 4 of Appendix I).

Table 7. Number of pubescence and length of a single bud of test clones and their control.

Test clones	Number of pubescence	length of a single unopen bud (cm)
Ph/9/68A	1452bc	2.56bc
Sh/D/11/18	1725a	3.32b
A/8/61	1386c	2.35c
SC/12/28	1631b	4.31a
BT2	1682ab	3.38b
LSD at 0.05 level of significance	61.98	0.48

Within row values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

Drought tolerance

The drought performances of the test clones and their control are given at Table 8. Test clone SC/12/28 provides highest values in Average depth of root at 3rd year, Proline Content, Total Chlorophyll, Chlorophyll Stability Index, Photosynthesis, Water Use Efficiency and Relative Leaf Water Content which was followed by test clone Sh/D/11/18, but both were higher than control BT2. On the other hand, in case of Leaf Water Potential and Transpiration both test clones SC/12/28 and Sh/D/11/18 provide lowest values than the control BT2. Kaloyereas (1958); El-Nadi (1969); Bota et al. (2004); Damayanthi et al. (2010) also reported that higher values for the average root depth at the

third year, the chlorophyll stability index, the proline content, the efficiency of photosynthesis and water utilization, and lower values for transpiration and leaf water potential suggest an increase in the degree of drought tolerance. So, the test clone SC/12/28 has been observed to be highly tolerant to drought while Sh/D/11/18 was found to be drought hardy than other test clones and the control.

Table 8. Drought performances of the test clones and their control.

Characteristics	Ph/9/68A	Sh/D/11/18	A/8/61	SC/12/28	BT2	LSD at 5% level of significance
Avrg. depth of root at 3 rd year (cm)	25.64c	31.14ab	26.61bc	33.18a	28.72b	2.45
Root Shoot Ratio	0.33	0.32	0.29	0.34	0.28	NS
Proline Content ($\mu\text{mol/g fr. wt}$)	0.51bc	0.56ab	0.48c	0.67a	0.55ab	0.09
Leaf Water Potential (LWP-bar)	11.96a	9.91bc	11.89ab	9.12c	10.33b	1.02
Total Chlorophyll (mg g^{-1})	6.12c	6.68ab	6.13c	7.67a	6.66b	0.003
Chlorophyll Stability Index (CSI%)	68.00bc	79.00b	67.00c	89.00a	88.00ab	1.31
Photosynthesis ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	8.28c	8.55bc	8.29c	9.55a	8.92b	0.80
Transpiration ($\text{m.mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	2.22a	2.05c	2.24a	2.01c	2.15b	0.02
Water Use Efficiency ($\mu\text{mol/m mol}$)	5.32b	5.89ab	5.31b	5.97a	5.85ab	0.005
Relative Leaf Water Content (RWC %)	61.24c	69.14ab	62.35bc	69.41a	68.22ab	1.82

Within row values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

Conclusion

Morphologically test clone Sh/D/11/18 is the light-leaved Assam agrotype which is key indicator for better quality while test clone SC/12/28 is China Monipuri Hybrid agrotype is for more drought tolerance. It was also found that, Sh/D/11/18 and SC/12/28 both test clones possess excellent rooting ability. On the other hand, test clone Sh/D/11/18, A/8/61 and SC/12/28 gave higher results in 100 fresh shoot weight, shoot length, leaf area, lamina length, serration/leaf, pruning sticks/bush at FFP-2 and plucking point /bush/year in most cases than the control BT2. But, in case of yield performance at mature stage, test clone SC/12/28 was found superior to other test clones which was followed by A/8/61 and Sh/D/11/18, both were statistically similar. However, for quality performance, Sh/D/11/18 test clone has been found to be 'Excellent' cup quality. On the basis of drought parameters, SC/12/28 has been observed to be highly tolerant to drought while Sh/D/11/18 was found to be drought hardy than other test clones. Considering the morphological, yield, quality and drought parameters, test clone Sh/D/11/18 were released as 'Improved Quality Clone' 'BT22' while SC/12/28 were released as 'Drought Tolerant Standard Clone' 'BT23' in the BT-series to the industry in 2021.

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Appendix I: Pictorial representation of BT22 (Sh/D/11/18) and BT23 (SC/12/28)

Fig. 1. Excellent rooting of BT22 (Sh/D/11/18)

Fig. 2. Pluckable section of BT23 (SC/12/28)

Fig. 3. Excellent cup quality of BT22 (Sh/D/11/18)

Fig. 4. Longest single unopen buds of BT23 (SC/12/28)